

A longitudinal Study of Distal and Proximal Indicators of Teacher Effectiveness and Students' Mathematics Competence in Germany

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Abstract

Recent research on teacher effectiveness has turned its focus from teacher factors (distal indicators) toward teaching factors (proximal indicators) because teaching factors are proximal to the instruction process. However, current study argued that the importance of distal indicators cannot be undermined. Therefore, the present study investigated both distal indicators and proximal indicators of mathematics teaching in a longitudinal manner using German National Educational Panel Study (NEPS) data. Students' mathematics competence was measured at the beginning of grade 5 and then, at the beginning of grade 7. Contrary to expectation, the study found that distal indicators are stronger predictor of student mathematics competence than proximal indicators. Furthermore, study also found that generally, German teachers lack in effectiveness and no significant differences were found among teacher effectiveness across academic and vocational school tracks which is thought provoking because teachers of academic school tracks are trained rigorously than their counterparts.

Introduction

The focus of research on educational effectiveness has turned from school effectiveness towards the effectiveness of the teachers as research in the recent past has shown that teachers are the most important determinant of student learning. However, there is still a lack of consensus as to whether distal indicators of instruction or proximal indicators of instruction are more important. Seidel and Shavelson (2007) claimed in their meta-analyses that teacher factors are in fact distal indicators of effectiveness whereas instructional factors are the proximal indicators of teacher effectiveness. Therefore, Seidel and Shavelson assumed in their study that proximal indicators are stronger predictors of student learning in comparison to distal indicators because they are proximal to teaching-learning process. Distal and proximal indicators are defined in terms of their proximity to the teaching-learning process. Seidel and Shavelson mentioned that correlational research is the most dominant design used in teacher effectiveness research, however, it has often examined teacher effectiveness through distal indicators and very little research has used proximal indicators in educational effectiveness research. This might be the reason behind the weak effects of teacher and their instruction on student learning as shown by previous correlational studies in comparison to quasi-experimental and experimental studies. Although, Seidel and Shavelson found proximal indicators as more effective than distal indicators in their meta-analyses study, there is important evidence showing distal indicators are an effective determinant of student learning, for instance well-known meta-meta-analyses of Hattie (2009), and this evidence cannot be ignored. Moreover, findings from a single meta-analyses study are not enough to diminish the significance of distal indicators. As there is no consensus in past research on the role of distal indicators of teaching in teacher effectiveness, there is plenty of room to further investigate this issue, particularly in the context of correlational research. More research is needed in correlational studies to investigate which indicators (distal or proximal) are more effective, particularly in similar research scenario. In particular, such research is required in correlational setting, which investigates the effectiveness of distal and proximal indicators in same setting. The present study has aimed at investigating the effectiveness of both distal indicators and proximal indicators in same research setting, on similar population with a condition that same teachers had taught students mathematics for the period of at least two years. The period of two years, is long enough to assert that change in students' competence is due to the recent mathematics teacher. Teacher effectiveness is defined as the effect of the current teacher on student mathematics competence while controlling for the previous mathematics competence.

Recently there has been a growing interest in examining teaching and learning in domain-specific contexts. Seidel and Shavelson (2007) found that studies in domain-specific contexts showed a greater effect on student learning than domain-general studies. Baumert et al. (2013) affirmed that teaching and learning are domain-specific and Hattie (2009) also provided the evidence that different teaching approaches show different effects on student learning in different domains. For instance, Hattie (2009) reported that constructivist teaching

is effective in mathematics teaching and direct instruction is effective for instruction in reading domain. Following this recent research trend, the current study has mainly examined the teacher effectiveness in a domain-specific context.

Another novel aspect of present study is teacher effectiveness is measured across school types on similar research instruments. Teachers in different school types in Germany are trained differently because teaching is differently challenged in school types on the basis of students' abilities. Baumert et al. (2013) argued, teachers of different school types differ in their characteristics and it is significant to examine if they also differ in their effectiveness. The data for current study is from different types of lower secondary schools in Germany, it offers the opportunity to analyze and compare the role of mathematics teachers and their instruction in students' mathematics competence development among schools.

Distal and Proximal Indicators of Teacher Effectiveness

Current models of teacher effectiveness measure teacher effectiveness proximal to the process of instruction and learning rather than distal indicators such as teacher factors. The idea of proximal indicators to the teaching-learning process is introduced by Seidel and Shavelson (2007) in their meta-analyses in which they found that proximal indicators are better indicators of measuring teacher effectiveness. Proximity is a matter of degree. The proximal indicators of measuring teacher effectiveness discussed by Seidel and Shavelson (2007) were used in experimental studies and quasi experimental studies because both research types could measure the process of instruction proximally. However, both methods are expensive ways of data collection and therefore, data is usually collected on small samples and in experimental conditions, which therefore, lack in generalizability. Furthermore, Seidel and Shavelson study has found that teacher effectiveness research is dominated by correlational studies in which distal indicators are used to measure teacher effectiveness, which they suggest is not the best way of measuring teacher effectiveness. Therefore, it is crucial to measure the instructional process in correlational studies with large sample size. Therefore, the current study is correlational in nature but has taken into account the idea of proximally measuring the teaching-learning process through an instructional questionnaire that directly asked teachers about their instructional practices in classroom. Although, proximal indicators may be the better way of measuring teacher effectiveness, does it mean distal indicators are no longer important? It is expected that distal indicators are important as they have the power to shape teachers' instruction. Empirical studies have shown that distal indicators influence instructional practices (Stipek, Givvin, Salmon & Macgyvers, 2001) and also student outcomes (Seidel & Shavelson, 2007). However, according to Seidel and Shavelson (2007) distal indicators are a less reliable way of measuring teacher effectiveness. Author argued that in order to get the clear picture of the role, the both distal indicators and proximal indicators determine in students' learning, both indicators needed to be investigated on similar data. Therefore, the current study measured teacher effectiveness through both distal indicators and proximal indicators.

In a nutshell, the present study has investigated distal and proximal indicators of teacher effectiveness in domain specific instruction in longitudinal setting (two yearlong) with students' mathematics competence measured at both beginning and end of the study.

Distal indicators

Baumert and Kunter (2013) affirmed that teachers play the most important role in the education system. Hattie stated that "the current mantra is that teachers make the difference" (2009, p.34). Therefore, abundant efforts are made in order to make teachers competent and effective. In Germany, teachers are trained in both subject-matter knowledge and pedagogical knowledge to ensure they are able to cope with the challenges they will face in the classroom and to help children learn to their maximum potential. Moreover, teachers are trained in relation to the school type in which they will teach. However, the research shows that although teacher training is systematic and well planned teachers are not effective in a similar way and it might be because there are certain habits, beliefs and pedagogical ideals of teachers that influence their instruction. Some previous studies have reported that teachers' practices are influenced by their general beliefs. For instance Baumert et al. (2010) have conducted a longitudinal study in Germany and have shown that teachers' beliefs and knowledge are related to students' outcomes and this relation was mediated by instructional practices. This shows that there are some factors that influence teacher instruction however, the findings are not conclusive. Therefore, the current study aimed to measure the effect of distal indicators on student outcomes in order to get a better understanding and empirical evidence about the effect of distal indicators. The distal indicators along with their definitions are given as follows. *Teacher belief* implies teachers' disposition about different aspects of teaching and learning. *Stress in teaching* means the stress teachers feel while lesson planning and in classroom. *Professional collaboration* implies planning and preparation of learning material and lessons together by teachers and participation in team discussions. *Exchange and coordination for teaching* states that exchanging of instructional material or discussing learning problems of individual students among colleagues.

Proximal indicators

The paradigm shift from teacher quality to instructional quality resulted in a focus on teacher instructional practices in the classroom. Moreover, this focus on instructional practices is rather specific i.e.

instruction with respect to the nature of the subject to be taught assuming that learning is domain-specific and it should be according to the nature of the subject. For instance, Hattie (2009) reported that constructivist teaching is effective in mathematics teaching and direct instruction is effective for instruction of reading. This is called domain-specific instruction. In Baumert and Kunter's (2013) words "teaching and learning are domain specific."

On the basis of the importance of instruction in recent models of teacher effectiveness current study has measured teachers' instructions in relation to the subject being taught (domain specific instruction). The process of learning is a multidimensional process which offers learning in a flow in which the teacher arranges learning in a social context and students participate in groups in the learning process actively, they interact, they argue, they discuss and move towards achieving their goal. They share and discuss their experiences and thoughts with the class and with other teachers and learn from their experiences and here the teacher has the chance to monitor and guide students and change the direction of their thoughts, if needed. Further, the teacher activates students' cognition by providing opportunities that critically analyze the domain or subject-matter being taught. This nature of proximal indicators is evident from the proximal constructs selected in this study and from their definitions given below.

Student engagement followed the definition by Newmann (1992) student engagement is defined as "the student's psychological investment in and effort directed toward learning, understanding or mastering the knowledge, skills or crafts that academic work is intended to promote." (p.12). *Cognitive activation* definition is adopted from Kunter et al. (2007), "the elements of instruction, meaning all learning situations with the potential to trigger students' conceptual involvement with the learning task." *Cognitively challenging tasks* implies tasks that activate student thinking and foster higher order learning. *Differentiation* is defined in the current study as defined by Tomlinson (2001), "differentiation is the recognition, articulation, and commitment to plan for students' differing needs."

The theoretical model of the study is presented in figure 1.

Mathematics Competence

The concept of measuring student mathematics competence in NEPS is not based on the idea of student mathematical achievement or student mastery on the content being taught; rather it is based on the ability of students to apply the learned knowledge in real life. NEPS has adopted this idea from the PISA study that defined it as an individual's ability to recognize, formulate and tackle mathematical problems in the context of real life which they term mathematical literacy. NEPS has defined mathematics competence similarly. In order to define mathematics competence in terms of practical knowledge is necessary to assess to what extent students are able to apply the learned knowledge in problems outside the context of the mathematics classroom. The concept of mathematical competence also reflects the teachers' skill to prepare students to apply the learned skills in real life situations and not only as the source of getting grades. As cited by NEPS mathematics competence in NEPS and therefore, in current study is based on the idea of mathematics literacy in PISA study and is defined as "an individual's capacity to identify and understand the role that mathematics plays in the world, to make well-founded mathematical judgments and to use and engage with mathematics in ways that meet the needs of that individual's life as a constructive, concerned and reflective citizen." (OECD, 2003, 24)

The Rationale of the Study

Following the PISA shock (results from first two PISA studies showed that German students are at-risk regarding their mathematics competence), a number of studies have been conducted on classroom instruction in recent years in Germany. These include PALMA study, COACTIV study and Structure as a quality feature in mathematics instruction (2007). The noteworthy findings of the studies are German students deficiency in mathematics competence is not only among 15 year olds (as shown by PISA 2000, 2003) but also at the beginning of secondary school and teachers' instruction is not sufficiently supporting the development of mathematics competence (PALMA, 2007). COACTIV study found that strong mathematics instruction aiming at insightful learning is rarely offered in German schools. *Structure as a quality feature in mathematics instruction* (2007) found that cognitive activation in instructional process leads to students' better mathematics achievement.

Although the above mentioned studies were longitudinal, quasi-experimental and well-designed, the sample was either not representative of the whole of Germany or the studies have drawn the sample from only a few school types. The current study is different in that the sample is representative of all of Germany, drawn from all school types within Germany and it's also a longitudinal study but correlational in nature, extended over the period of two years that measured student mathematics competence both at the beginning and at the end of the two years. The study took place in a natural setting and the classes are taken into study intact. Moreover, their findings of these are not conclusive. Furthermore, COACTIV suggested that additional studies are needed in the domain of mathematics with teachers from different school types and training backgrounds before the final conclusions are made from the findings of the study (Kunter et al., 2013). The current study would provide detailed findings about a variety of distal and proximal indicators and their effect on student mathematics competence over the period of two years.

This question analyzed how teachers in lower secondary school, middle secondary school, multi-track school, comprehensive school and grammar school vary in effectiveness. In Germany, more competent teachers are selected and trained for higher school tracks and the less competent teachers are trained for the lower school tracks. Moreover, the teachers for different school tracks are trained differently in Germany. For instance, the teachers for the academic school track are trained with a focus on content knowledge and teachers for non-academic school tracks are trained with a focus on pedagogical knowledge. The concept behind this is that the teachers in the academic track would have to face more challenging situations with respect to the content of the subject and the teachers in the non-academic tracks would need more pedagogical skills to teach students with comparatively low competence. As the teachers in different school tracks have different level of competence and have attended different teacher training they might vary in effectiveness too.

School System and Teacher Education in Germany

As the sample of the study is from Germany, it is important to understand the unique German school system and teacher education system before proceeding into further details of the study. The most distinct feature of the German school system is the placement of children in various school tracks at an early age (around 10 years) on the basis of their cognitive abilities, perceived performance, and interest. There are 4 main different types of schools in which students are tracked after their elementary education. These schools generally teach the same courses, however, the curriculum varies not only in each school type but also in each school.

Lower secondary school (Hauptschule) provides a basic general education with a focus on vocational and hands-on training. The second school type, middle secondary school (Realschule) offers a more extensive general education than lower secondary school. Middle secondary school (Gymnasium) is higher in academic level than lower secondary school and lower than grammar school. Grammar school is the most academically challenging school type in Germany that teaches the extensive general education. Another type of school called Comprehensive school (Gesamtschule) enrolls students from different academic levels at the same school and assigns a certificate to them at the end of school according to their academic level. In Comprehensive schools, students with similar abilities are taught together (cooperative type) or students are taught together as a year group except for the core subjects in which they are grouped on the basis of their ability.

The teacher education system in Germany is highly systematic and goes hand in hand with the German school system i.e. German teacher education programs differ on the basis of age level (elementary or secondary) and the type of school. In general, teacher education programs are comprised of 2 phases. In phase I, teachers are trained for a period of 3-5 years at college. At the end of this training, the teacher has to pass a state examination which is followed by in-service teacher training in which teachers are mentored by experienced teachers and supervised by the state run teacher education institute where they also attend weekly seminars (Cortina & Thames, 2013). This in-service training lasts from one and a half to two years and is followed by the second state examination. After passing both examinations, teachers are usually employed at the type of school they are trained for with very little pressure to attend any further professional training and assessments in the rest of their career. Hence, Germany has a unique school system and teacher education system that could play a significant role in students' performance.

Methodology

Total number of elements from which subjects are selected are called population (Siddique et al., 2020; Siddique et al., 2021; Sajjad et al., 2022). The present study used data from National Educational panel Data Study, NEPS. The study uses NEPS's cohort 3 secondary school data which collects data at three time points, first at the beginning of grade 5 from the teachers and the students, then in grade 6 from teachers and finally in the beginning of grade 7 from students. During this two year period students were taught by the same mathematics teachers. In this first wave, the data was collected from teachers on the distal indicator questionnaire and students' mathematics competence was measured in the beginning of grade 5. In the second wave, in grade 6, data was collected again in the beginning of grade 6 however only the data on teachers' mathematics instructional questionnaire was collected. In the third and the final wave, the data was collected in grade 7 on the students' mathematics competence. The data about teachers' instruction was collected in the middle of the study which was an ideal time to capture the teachers' instructional practices. Students' mathematics competence was measured at two time points. At the time of measurement of mathematics competence in grade 7, it is likely that there were new mathematics teachers, however as those teachers had been teaching for only two to three months at the time of the competence test, the current study assumes that any effect on students' mathematics competence was from the teachers who taught them since previous two years.

Sample

Number of individuals selected from the population is called sample (Ali et al., 2021; Siddique et al., 2021; Siddique et al., 2021). The NEPS cohort 3 (grade 5), used multistage stratified cluster sampling which was drawn from officially recognized and state-approved secondary schools in Germany (Zinn, 2013). At the first stage of the selection process, the aforementioned types of schools were distinguished from

all over Germany. These school types served as stratum from which the schools were drawn proportionally to their number of classes.

Next, from those selected schools, grade 5 classes were randomly selected. Two classes were selected from each school (if available). In the third and final stage of sampling, all the students and teachers from the selected classes were invited to participate in the study.

The total sample consisted of 243 schools and approximately 5327 students and their mathematics teachers which were over 500 in number. However, because of the longitudinal nature of the study and that it was essential that the same mathematics teachers taught the students for the full period of 2 years, all the teachers who had taught less than 2 years were excluded from the study. Hence, the students of those teachers were also excluded from the study. Then, the final sample size was 174 schools, 1906 students and their 174 teachers. However, the students from elementary schools also needed to be excluded from the study at hand because of the structure of this school type. The structure of elementary school is different from other school types. Generally in German schools students are allocated to different academic tracks after grade 4 and then usually they study in the same school for the rest of their school years. But from the total 16 states of Germany, two states (Berlin and Brandenburg) allocate students to different academic tracks (on the basis of their abilities) after grade 6. This means in these types of schools, students are allocated to different school types in grade 7 and not in grade 5 like other schools of Germany. In the study design, time point 2 mathematics competence was measured in grade 7, the students in these two states were dispersed to different schools. For this reason it was not possible for NEPS to collect data from them therefore, the data on grade 7 mathematics competence of elementary school students was missing. Hence, students from these school types were excluded from the study. The students who did not participate in the mathematics competence test at both time points were also excluded from the study. However, if the students only participated at one time point and not the other, they were not excluded as almost 24% of the sample students' were missing at time point 1 or at time point 2. The exclusion of this many students would result in a large loss of sample size. Therefore, they were kept in the study and the data was imputed. Data imputation is a rather new statistical technique that replaces missing data by estimating values on the basis of available information. It is a better method of tackling with missing value in comparison to other methods (list wise and pairwise deletion) because it avoids sample bias. The procedure of multiple imputation is described by Newmann (2003) as "a procedure by which missing data are imputed several times (e.g., using regression imputation) to produce several different complete-data estimates of the parameters. The parameter estimates from each imputation are then combined to give an overall estimate of the complete-data parameters as well as reasonable estimates of the standard errors". The data was imputed by Full Information Maximum Likelihood Estimation (FIML) in Mplus. Multiple data sets were generated using multiple imputation in Mplus. In the current study, 1000 data sets were generated in each analyses to get consistent and reliable results.

The final sample is drawn from 5 school types (lower secondary school, middle secondary school, grammar school, comprehensive school and multi-track school). The sample comprised of 151 schools, 1660 students (male = 843, female = 804, missing = 13) and their 151 teachers (male = 41, female = 73, missing = 37). The details about students and teachers according to each school type are given in table 1.

Research Questions

1. Which distal indicators predict mathematics competence development of lower secondary school students?
2. Which proximal indicators predict mathematics competence development of lower secondary school students?
3. Do teachers in different school tracks vary in effectiveness?

This question analyzed how teachers in lower secondary school, middle secondary school, multi-track school, comprehensive school and grammar school vary in effectiveness. In Germany, more competent teachers are selected and trained for higher school tracks and the less competent teachers are trained for the lower school tracks. Moreover, the teachers for different school tracks are trained differently in Germany. For instance, the teachers for the academic school track are trained with a focus on content knowledge and teachers for non-academic school tracks are trained with a focus on pedagogical knowledge. The concept behind this is that the teachers in the academic track would have to face more challenging situations with respect to the content of the subject and the teachers in the non-academic tracks would need more pedagogical skills to teach students with comparatively low competence. As the teachers in different school tracks have different level of competence and have attended different teacher training they might vary in effectiveness too.

Instruments of the Study

Three instruments were used in current study; distal indicators questionnaire, proximal indicators questionnaire and mathematics competence tests. All the instruments of the study were developed and administered in the German language. The details about instrument used in the present study are as follows.

Distal indicators questionnaire and proximal indicators questionnaire. The distal indicators questionnaire is a self-report questionnaire which measures information about socio-demographic data, educational training and pedagogical ideals and concepts (Frahm et. al., 2011). However, proximal indicators questionnaire only

measured about mathematics instruction. Data was collected on 5 point Likert scale and on 6 point Likert scale from some scales. Confirmatory factor analyses was performed in order to confirm the construct validity of both questionnaires. CFA is a theory driven technique that statistically determines the relationship between the observed and unobserved variables (Schreiber et. al., 2010). The CFA models were specified and estimated in the Mplus version 7.11 with restricted maximum likelihood estimation (Muthén & Muthén, 1998-2015). It is important to note that the CFA was performed not only on the teachers that are included in the study but also on the teachers that were excluded from the study for not having taught for the period of two years. The large sample size for CFA is helpful for the stability of parameters. Therefore, the sample is bigger than the sample of the current study i.e. ($N = 642$). The items showed good factors loadings for each construct i.e. above 0.40 as recommended by Hair, Anderson, Tatham and Black (1998). Sample item for each variable is mentioned in table 2 along with Cronbach alpha reliability.

Mathematics competence test. The mathematics competence tests aim to measure students' ability to apply mathematics knowledge and skills in real life situations. The framework of the test is based on two dimensions to structure mathematical processes: content areas and cognitive components (Schnittjer & Duchhardt, 2015). These content areas are quantity, space and shape, change and relationships, data and chance. The Grade 5 competence test consisted of 24 items and grade 7 competence test consisted of 23 items. A WLE (weighted maximum likelihood estimate) was used as the measure of mathematics competence in the current study instead of sum scores. Like a sum score, WLE does not take into account the measurement error, however, WLE better estimates individual scores and therefore, students' ability in comparison to sum score as WLE facilitates both the adequate treatment of missing responses and comparability of competence scores longitudinally (Pohl & Carstensen, 2012).

Data Analyses

Data was analyzed by using the Mplus software package version 7.11. Although, the data has a multilevel structure, with students nested in teachers, the study has single level analyses. The reason for not doing the multilevel analyses is the study aimed to measure the individual competence of students, not at the class level, because in multilevel analyses the class mean is taken into account. Secondly, for multilevel analyses the class size should be meaningfully large. However, in the current study, in some cases the class size is very small. Therefore, for multilevel analyses, it would be needed to delete the teachers with small numbers of students which would result in a small sample size. However, the study has taken into account the multilevel structure of the sample by using TYPE = COMPLEX in the analyses. Type = COMPLEX do corrections to the standard error and chi-square of the model fit that takes into account stratification, non-independence of observations, and unequal probability of selection (Muthén & Muthén, 1998-2015). The data was analyzed through the application of multiple regression, and multi-group analyses according to the research questions. Descriptive data of teachers is presented in table 3.

Empirical Findings

Before moving to the results from the main research questions of the study, the control variables of the study are discussed. Some important student factors that could predict students' competence on a theoretical basis are student gender, students' MC5, socio-economic status (SES), students' migration background and school type. The current study has assumed that factors like student gender, socio-economic status (SES) and migration background already has an influence in the students' MC5. Therefore, only MC5 and school type were included as control variables in the study. This balanced selection of the control variables would help to not overestimate or under estimate the effect of distal indicator on students' grade 7 mathematics competence. A multiple linear regression analyses was performed using both control variables to see if both variables predict grade 7 mathematics competence. The results showed that MC5 is strong predictor of MC7 ($\beta = .70^*$), however school type did not show any significant effect ($\beta = .11$). 56% of the total variance was explained by MC5.

The model fit for all research questions was tested through the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and Standard Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), CFI values above 0.90 show an adequate fit (HU & Bentler, 1999) and for RMSEA and SRMR values less than 0.08 indicate reasonable error of approximation in the sample (Browne & Cudeck, 1989).

Research Question 1

What distal indicators predict mathematics competence of lower secondary school students?

This question was analyzed by performing multiple regression analyses on distal indicators to see the effect of these indicators on mathematics competence of grade 7. The regression model and its result along with the correlations between distal indicators are presented in figure 2. Detailed results are shown in table 4. The results showed that teacher belief, professional collaboration and teaching stress significantly predicted MC7, and however, the effect is weak. Distal indicators explained 11% of the total variance.

Research Question 2

What proximal indicators predict mathematics competence of lower secondary school students?

This question was analyzed by performing multiple regressions analyses on proximal indicators to see the effect of these indicators on mathematics competence grade 7. The regression model and its result along

with the correlations between proximal indicators are presented in figure 3. Detailed results are shown in table 5. The results showed that all indicators except cognitive activation significantly predicted MC7, however the effect is weak. Proximal indicators explained 6% of the total variance.

Research Question 3

Do teachers in different school tracks vary in effectiveness?

A multi-group analyses was performed in Mplus 7.11 to investigate this research question. Multiple regression was performed on all the distal indicators and proximal indicators along with MC5 on 5 school types including lower secondary school, middle secondary school, multi-track school, comprehensive school and grammar school. The aim was to measure if students from any of these school types are at a disadvantage with regard to their teachers' effectiveness. The analyses was performed by controlling students' MC5. The results showed that only student engagement significantly predicted MC7 in multi-track school and stress in planning and classroom significantly predicted MC7 in grammar school, however the effect is low in both cases. None of the other distal or proximal indicator showed any effect on MC7. From these results we can say that students own competence is the main sole predictor of their future competence. The result of regression model along with correlation between proximal indicators is presented in figure 3.

Discussion

Among the distal indicators, teacher belief, professional collaboration and stress in teaching significantly predicted students' mathematics competence. However, among those indicators only teacher belief has a positive effect on students' mathematics competence and the rest of the indicators showed negative effects. Theoretically, the significant effect of teacher belief is plausible because previous research has found support for teachers' beliefs influencing their behavior in the planning and classroom (Pajares, 1992) and teacher classroom behavior influencing student outcome (TALIS, 2009). Moreover, Kunter et al. (2013) considers different dimensions of teacher belief as the foundation of quality teaching. The negative effect of stress in teaching was, as expected, because stress in teaching may be an indication that teacher is not able to cope with the challenges of teaching. Professional collaboration has a negative effect, which was not expected and it is difficult to suggest why. However, it was found that more experienced teachers collaborate less than less experienced teachers. Thus it may be that less experienced teachers need assistance in teaching and therefore, they collaborate more which shows a negative effect, which is actually not the effect of collaboration rather their lack of expertise in teaching. Among the proximal indicators, the current study has found that student engagement, cognitively challenging tasks and differentiation have a significant effect on students' competence. These findings were in line with the findings from previous research about student engagement (Brozo, Shiel & Topping, 2008; Yair, 2007; Kirsch et al. 2002; Farkas et al., 1990) and cognitively challenging tasks (Pianta & Hamre, 2009; Rakoczy, 2007; Hamre & Pianta, 2005). Furthermore Hattie's (2009) meta-meta-analyses showed a significant effect of cognitively challenging goals on student outcomes.

Cognitive activation weakly but positively predicted mathematics competence in the current study which is not in line with the results from the previous studies (Kunter et al., 2013; Baumert et al., 2010; Rakoczy, 2007) that found that cognitive activation is a strong predictor of student achievement. Therefore, in this study, cognitive activation should have shown positive effects on student competence given that teachers had scored moderate to high on the usage of cognitive activation during instruction. This may be because teachers do not do effective use of cognitive activation or teachers who don't practice cognitive activation in their classroom also reported that they practice cognitive activation in classrooms because it is socially desirable to do so. Therefore, teachers' self-report might not be a reliable way of measuring cognitive activation because the studies that showed positive effects of cognitive activation have measured cognitive activation through other means for instance students interviews. It is also supported by the findings from the Kunter et al. (2007) which reported that German secondary classrooms generally lack in the practice of cognitive activation.

The current study found the negative effect of differentiation on student competence which was not expected on the basis of theory, however, the previous research on differentiation showed mixed results with some studies showing a positive effect of differentiation on student achievement and some showing negative effects (Scheerens, 2007). He found in his meta-analyses study in mathematics teaching that differentiation showed a positive effect in 25 studies, 9 studies showed negative effects and 66 studies showed no significant effect and in other subjects in general, differentiation showed a negligible effect. Tomlinson (2001) stated that often teachers understand differentiation as assigning more work to some students and less to others, which is not accurate and is ineffective. He further added for effective use of differentiation, content, process and product are very important, however, differentiation does not mean to expect different levels of outcomes from students with different abilities as Gamoran and Weinstein (1998) also stated that equity is a condition for differentiation.

Previous research suggested that proximal indicators are more important than distal indicators in determining student learning (Seidel & Shavelson, 2007). However, the results from the current study showed that distal indicators turned out to be more significant in determining student competence in comparison with proximal indicators as distal indicators explained 11% of the variance and proximal indicators only explained 6% of the total variance in student competence. Although, it is not claimed that proximal indicators are less

important than distal indicators, it surely suggests that distal indicators are equally important in determining teacher effectiveness. Contrary to suggestion of past research (Seidel and Shavelson, 2007), this showed that distal indicators cannot be overlooked while measuring teacher effectiveness.

A low effect of proximal indicators on student mathematics competence confirmed the findings from the previous studies like Pekrun et al. (2007) who reported in the findings from the PALMA study that in Bavaria, teachers' instruction lacks in effectiveness and their instruction is insufficient to increase student learning. Moreover, Kunter et al. (2007) reported that instructional strategies that promote insightful learning are barely offered in German schools. The low effects of effective instructional strategies like cognitive activation showed that German teachers need to improve those instructional strategies both in quantity and quality.

From the results from different school types, none of the distal indicator and proximal indicator appeared as significant in relation to student competence development when MC5 was controlled for. No particular pattern was found in the results except students' previous competence as the sole predictor of later competence among all school types. The only significant predictor in grammar schools was stress in teaching showing a negative effect on competence and student engagement in multi-track schools showed a positive effect on competence. This showed that teachers at grammar schools may lack in planning and the skills required in class. Baumert et al. (2010) found that students' with high previous knowledge require teachers with high subject matter knowledge. However, the results from the current study showed that students with higher prior knowledge not only need teachers with high subject-matter knowledge but also with high teaching skills so that they won't experience stress in teaching activities. No effect of the large range of distal and proximal indicators on student outcomes in each school type suggests that teacher may lack in professional skills and that professional training needs to be improved to contribute to students' learning according to their needs.

Limitations

One of the limitations of this research is the data on the distal indicators questionnaire was not measured specifically in relation to mathematics teaching. However, the data about proximal indicators was measured in relation to their mathematics teaching.

Due to the longitudinal structure of the study, many teachers and students were excluded from the study for not being in the same class for the period of two years. Teachers who taught less than the period of two years were excluded from the study and, therefore, their students were also excluded from the study. However, the sample bias was measured by comparing the responses of teachers on questionnaires between teachers who remained in the study and the teachers who were excluded and no significant differences were found among both groups. 25% of the final teacher sample that taught students for the period of two years declined to respond to the questionnaires, however, the missing data was completely at random and therefore, it was imputed to deal with the missing values. The reliability of some indicators was low but it was reasonable to be used and showed significant effects.

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